

The Effectiveness of Internet Marketing in Increasing the Reach and Awareness on Consumer in Bahrain

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ABSTRACT

The present research seeks to expound the effective of Internet marketing in increasing the reach and awareness of consumers. Impatient the research conducted a good review about the privies literature related to the study. It leads a brief idea of the study before articulating the statement of the problem. From the statement of the problem deducting the researcher found that the social media , mobile apps and internet marketing have Promina impact with the effectiveness and in cornering the awareness of the consumer .hence the research subdivided the research problem into four different objective such translates the formation of the study states that these is no significant relationship between level of effectiveness and level of utilization of internet marketing on consumer in kingdom of Bahrain . Further the research employs multiple methodologies to a new conclusion on the particular issue, the study used convening sampling method combined with the spss software for data analyse.

The study aims to assess the Effectiveness of Internet in Business to increase reach and awareness among consumers in Bahrain. Data and correspondence innovation has changed quickly in the previous 20 years with a key advancement being the development of online networking. Business, which does not utilize internet-based life, tends to lose on key client base. The rise of social media means it's unusual to find an organization that does not reach its customers and prospects through one social media platform or another. Companies see the importance of using social media to connect with customers and build revenue.

Businesses have realized they can use social media to generate insights, stimulate demand, and create targeted product offerings. This is important in traditional brick-and-mortar businesses, and, obviously, in the world of e-commerce.

In this research, to adequately address the research questions a variety of data collection methods and instruments were used such as questionnaire survey and t-test.

From the study, the researcher concluded that there is no significant relationship between the Level of utilization & Effectiveness of Internet marketing among consumers in Bahrain. Therefore, the researchers accept the null hypothesis.

The problems faced by the respondents on the Level of utilization & Effectiveness of Internet marketing among consumers in Bahrain is privacy, censorship and online security. The Internet, social media, online advertising, mobile apps etc. as a whole, can be seen as technology that has greatly enhanced our lives but should be done responsibly.

Keywords-- Internet, Business, Marketing, ARPANET

I. INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Internet has developed immensely in the applications and number of clients because of its special qualities of adaptability, intuitiveness, and personalization. It has been an exceptionally valuable instrument for correspondence, excitement, training, and electronic exchange (ko et al., 2013; koyuncu and lien, 2013). The progressive change delivered by data innovation importantly affects the day by day lives. It has changed the way we work together by enabling retailers to offer boundless scope of items and administrations to all customers from around the globe anytime.

The web has created as an advancing medium (silk et al., 2011). Various associations have swung to the Internet to broadcast their things and organizations; and the Internet is regarded to be the hugest direct advancing channel for the overall business focus (faber et al., 2012; ko et al., 2012; korgaonkar and wolin, 2012). Associations are purging billions of dollars into web elevating to gain more conspicuous quantifiable benefit on ads (edwards, 2010; joines et al.,2013).

The internet has given purchasers more control in getting to data on items and administrations. There are factors that add to shoppers pull for online substance—buyers are the person who choose when, where, what, and how much business content they wish to see (korgaonkar and wolin, 2012). The Internet empowers customers to get to a boundless scope of items and administrations from organizations around the globe, and it has diminished the time and exertion they spend on shopping (ko et al., 2012).

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Customers play a considerably more dynamic part in hunting down data online because of some objective, and that objective can impact singular practices and reactions to online data and notices (smith, 2017). With the quick progression in the PC business, numerous customers have influenced the Internet as a component of their buy to blend to exploit the online advancements (calisir, 2011). The web has turned into a mainstream promoting stage since advertisers found that the web have more prominent adaptability and control over the publicizing materials (ducoffe, 19). Since the web can be utilized as an effective showcasing specialized apparatus, the two researchers and experts are keen on seeing how to take full preferred standpoint and boosting the estimation of this correspondence medium (rodgers and thorson, 2013).

Customers inside have been to a great extent presented to the conventional promoting frames as the primary media utilized by sponsors to give data. Be that as it may, throughout the years showcasing systems have developed with innovation prompting the web making extraordinary open doors for advanced advertisers to interface with clients to make an immersive associated computerized condition, impact and drive buys, fuel new development and make new piece of the overall industry. The development of web promoting is both all inclusive and locally outpacing disconnected publicizing.

Statement of the Study

The study aims to assess the Effectiveness of Internet in Business to increase reach and awareness among consumers in Bahrain. Specifically, The following are the main research objectives that guided the conduct of the entire research,

Data and correspondence innovation has changed quickly finished the previous 20 years with a key advancement being the development of online networking. Business, which does not utilize internet based life, has a tendency to lose on key client base.

Businesses have acknowledged they can utilize internet based life to produce experiences, empower request, and make focused on item contributions. This is critical in customary block and-engine organizations, and, clearly, in the realm of internet business.

1. What is the Level of utilization of Internet among consumers in terms of:
 - 1.1 Using Social Media
 - 1.2 Using Online Advertising
 - 1.3 Using Mobile Apps
2. What is the Level of Effectiveness of Internet reach and awareness among consumers in terms of:
 - 2.1 Using Social media
 - 2.2 Using Online Advertising
 - 2.3 Using mobile Apps

3. What is the relation between the Level of utilization and the Level of Effectiveness of among consumers?
4. What are the problems encountered in the process of utilization and effectiveness?

The purposes or objectives of marketing research are listed below

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE AND STUDIES

This section will talk about the related writing and studies, the remote and nearby ideas and furthermore the hypothetical and calculated systems. The different ideas and points of view helped the analyst to decide the examination issue, characterize the terms utilized, build up the strategy for this investigation and encourage a complete examination and comprehension of the exploration question. In this manner, the hypothetical and calculated structures were defined.

Publicists are relied upon to move and burn through millions in internet promoting in the coming a very long time than television, print advertisements and other conventional publicizing media. Internet promoting extensively comprises of different business content organizations conveyed by video clasp, print, and sound; either requested or spontaneous and incorporates organization sites, corporate logos, email messages, pop-ups, pennant advertisements, high rise promotions, catches, interstitials, hyperlinks, dynamic media, and intelligent recreations (ducoffe, 2016; goldsmith and lafferty, 2012; korgaonkar and wolin, 2012; wolin and korganokar, 2013).

With the fast development in innovation, the internet is turning into an essential one stop point for customers in discovering a large portion of their needs. Be it correspondence, stimulation, shopping, data seek, Internet fills in as a panacea for every one of their necessities. This has driven 70% of the ever customers to stick themselves to the web and access it all the time. The issue is that, volumes of customers are online consistently for their own work, yet do they see the advertisements, pennants and so on. Shown on that website page, most vital what is their review/recognition esteem. Shouldn't something be said about the scope of Internet promoting, is it viable crosswise over finished all objective gatherings?

While a lot of research has been done on advancing, the amplexness of electronic publicizing in is an area that has been truant from these examinations. Research done by wanjoga, (2012) for the most part centered around shopper demeanors towards web based publicizing in nairobi, and demonstrated that customers knew about the online adverts however with no inclination to the promoting frames. It in any case, neglected to measure and clarify the viability of internet web advancing on such clients. Relative

research done by wakukha, (2011) on the use of web publicizing by wireless industry, cleared up sorts of web advancing being utilized, the accomplishment and challenges looked in its use and the level of appointment, anyway fail to give information on its sufficiency in influencing or quickening client response.

The revelations of an investigation of the demeanor of buyers towards retail media advancing by tobacco firms in , showed that the customers know and found out about retail media publicizing mechanical assemblies. The examination used a case of 200 customers from retail outlets in nairobi, which was not a sensible case to choose its feasibility on all purchasers from . In any case, as proposed by gong and maddox (2013), "future research can investigate the effect of web promoting crosswise over various nations and societies to upgrade the worldwide comprehension of web publicizing viability" (p: 46). Also, more examinations are expected to cover different examples in various nations to expand outside legitimacy of the exploration discoveries (calisir, 2013).

Brad (2018) In 2011, Internet publicizing livelihoods in the United States outflanked those of advanced TV and nearly outperformed those of convey TV. In 2013, Internet publicizing livelihoods in the United States totaled \$42.8 billion, a 17% extension over the \$36.57 billion in earnings in 2012. U.S. web commercial salary hit an essential high of \$20.1 billion for the essential bit of 2013, up 18% over a comparable period in 2012. Web based publicizing is broadly utilized crosswise over for all intents and purposes all industry areas.

Numerous regular web based publicizing hones are disputable and progressively subject to direction. Online advertisement incomes may not satisfactorily supplant other distributors' income streams. Declining promotion income has driven a few distributors to shroud their substance behind paywalls.

There are no ensures that what the buyer really encounters will be the full of feeling reaction the publicist planned to make: look into has demonstrated that this sort of jumble between sponsor goals and purchaser reaction happens very regularly (cotte, coulter and moore, 2014; englis 1990; strong, homerand liu 1990).

These experiences in any case, various basic inquiries stay unanswered as for promotion bids. Why, for example, do these interests actuate such effective purchaser

reactions in specific cases? What makes them be pretty much successful on customers? , has the client made any buy after chaperon a promotions ? , do the client search for offers on internet before do any buy ? , With particular reference to internet promoting, this examination will endeavor to answer these inquiries. Effectiveness" (p: 46). What's more, more examinations are expected to cover different examples in various nations to build outside legitimacy of the exploration discoveries (calisir, 2013).

Established molding is regularly alluded to as methods in which people learn by affiliation. In the traditional molding worldview, pavlov's puppy, an unbiased boost is combined with an unconditioned jar to motivate an unconditioned response. For example, after reiterated pairings of meat (known to cause salivation) with the sound of a toll, the sound of a ringer alone summons salivation. This alliance is liable to two characteristics of the connection: contiguity and repeat. The law of contiguity communicates that all together for helpful making sense of how to happen, the unconditioned jar and the fair-minded lift must be coordinated close in order to each other. Furthermore, it isn't adequate for an unprejudiced jar and an unconditioned lift to simply exist together in a close-by time period. The more normal the mixing, the more straightforward it is to outline an alliance.

Defenders of applying established molding to advertising trust that the relationship between an item and positive jolts may help clarify the impact of numerous factors in correspondence and state of mind change.

In any case, these impacts were lessened in circumstances where buyers were in an unmistakable basic leadership mode. The learning's of established molding give us some understanding on the qualities of a successfully marked internet commercial. Above all else, the recurrence with which an advertisement is served impacts mark mindfulness. Recurrence likewise impacts whether or not, a relationship between a message and a brand a purchaser makes.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework included with theories, principles and research findings interrelated concept which are related to the study.

This is the framework on how this study is organised or developed and the theatrical framework of the present research is based on the work of kim and ko 2010.

Figure 2: Theoretical Framework of the study on the effectiveness of Internet marketing.

The paradigm above shows the conceptual framework of the study. It is an abstract representation of what the internet marketing. It shows the variables that the researcher shall examine to determine which of the three variables correlate most with customer satisfaction.

In beginning of the Internet, web based promoting was for the most part denied. For instance, two of the antecedent systems to the Internet, ARPANET and NSFNet, had "satisfactory utilize strategies" that restricted system "use for business exercises by revenue driven foundations.. Through website streamlining, pay-per-click publicizing, email promoting and nearby records, you can interface with a ready crowd. The clients are looking towards the Internet to discover neighbourhood administrations and merchandise.

III. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The findings of the survey are derived from the numerical data from the population of Bahrain as internet users. The interpretations of the findings, which are used to achieve the objectives of the study, are presented in this chapter.

The study aimed to assess the level of utilization and effectiveness of Internet marketing to increase reach and awareness among consumers by using social media, online advertisement and Mobile apps. The treatment of data revealed the following essential findings:

1- The findings of the perceptions of the respondents on the Level of utilization of Internet among consumers with a total weighted mean of 3.512, i.e. they agree with the questionnaire statements on the elements: Using online Advertising, Using Social Media, Using Mobile Apps .Moreover the respondents are utilizing the social media, online advertisement and mobile apps regularly for their education and business irrespective of age difference .

2- The findings of the perceptions of the respondents on the Effectiveness of Internet marketing to increase reach and awareness among consumers were as follows:

2.1 In terms of using social media, the consumers are undecided with a total weighted mean of 2.898, i.e. they are neither effective nor ineffective.

2.2 In terms of using online advertising, the consumers feel it useful and agree with a total weighted mean of 4.394, i.e. they are effective

2.3 In terms of using mobile apps, the consumers feel strongly about it with a total weighted mean of 4.448, i.e. they are effective.

3- There is no significant relationship between the Level of utilization & Effectiveness of Internet marketing among consumers in Bahrain. Therefore, the researchers accept the null hypothesis.

4- One of the biggest problems faced by the respondents on the Level of utilization & Effectiveness of Internet marketing among consumers in Bahrain is privacy, censorship and online security.

5- The Internet, social media, online advertising, mobile apps etc. as a whole, can be seen as technology that has greatly enhanced our lives but should be done responsibly.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, the conclusions on the Level of utilization of Internet among consumers the respondents agree with the questionnaire statements, On the Effectiveness of Internet marketing to increase reach and awareness among consumers, feel it is very effective the hypothesis of the study is accepted on the different variables of the study. The researchers accept the null hypothesis as there is no significant relationship between the Level of utilization & Effectiveness of Internet marketing among consumers in Bahrain. There is a need to completely implement effective responsibility for internet usage

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings and the conclusion, the following recommendations are made:

It comes as no surprise that successful relationship in both business and personal life depends entirely on active communication and it's the same with using the internet.

1. Adhere to general Internet etiquette

One of the ways to communicate effectively online is to follow to the later the general principle of online netiquette, which is the show and practice of respect and courtesy in an online environment.

2. Choose the right online media, popular Photos, music or videos that are available on the internet

It is true there are various media for online communication, but some of them work better for a given situation than in others. For instance, if you're releasing a new product, you would perhaps want to demonstrate how to use the product online.

3. Build a favorable online persona

If wan the consumer wants to communicate effectively online, then you must create a pleasant online persona. To achieve this objective, you start by managing your conduct carefully in a manner that adds an aura of competence, empathy, and professionalism to your persona.

FUTURE STUDIES

As the researcher has taken very specific subject on internet utilization and effectiveness in Bahrain. The researcher acknowledges that internet technology has changed our lives and the way we do business or socializing. The research needs further study to understand the various issues such as privacy, censorship and online security.

The Internet is the superior mean of communication and information dissemination in the new millennium. It is important to note out that searching for information on the Internet does not necessarily mean that some kind of learning process is going on. While the Internet dramatically changed the dissemination and sharing of information, there is no general consent among researches on the impact of the Internet on students' and learner's knowledge retention. Using the Internet as a source of information, the student's knowledge acquisition level and knowledge retention maybe affected for both the short term and long term.

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